

The Food Consumption Pattern of the Elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State

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Abstract

This study investigated the food consumption pattern of the elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State. The World Health Organisation's definition of elderly is "persons of 60 years of age or older" (WHO, 2002). Data were gathered from 25 males and 25 females elderly from five selected areas in the local government (Odojomu, Okeagunla, Ijoka, Odosida and Sora) through open ended questionnaire. Data collected were analyzed with the use of frequencies and simple percentage. Most of the elderly (62%) were female, 26% were above 60 years, 66% had no knowledge of exposure to early morning sunlight. Elderly in this area consumed more carbohydrate foods than other foods as 63%, 28% and 74% take either pounded yam, eba, amala, fufu, rice, pap, potato or water yam as breakfast, lunch and supper respectively. Very few (8% and 4%) take beans only as breakfast and lunch respectively. In view of the findings, it was recommended that government (Federal, State and Local) should organize public talks and lectures for the elderly on appropriate foods to be consumed by them to avoid diseases and to have more healthy aged years.

Introduction

An elderly person is one whose age is 60 years or above (WHO, 2002). Physical activities are reduced in this group of people and energy expenditure is also reduced. The quantity of energy food for the elderly should be slightly decreased, (Amerin 1996).

Their need for protein, vitamins and minerals remain unchanged. It could be necessary to give supplementary vitamin D to the elderly if he spends most of his time indoors.

An elderly person who has problems with his digestive and absorptive processes may require dietary advice, dental problems may prevent some elderly people from taking adequate diet. Cooking methods that aids digestion need to be adopted in preparing meals for the elderly. Foods that does not digest easily such as oily or fried foods should be avoided by them.

Donal (2000) stated that a good supply of green vegetables and fruits is necessary to meet the need for folic acid, other vitamins and roughage. The elderly require plenty of liquids in the form of water and milk in order to remain balanced and active as possible. This helps to stimulate digestion and strengthen bones and muscle.

Some elderly people eat certain foods and reject some for different reasons, some believe in taboos and cultural restrictions, some have likes and dislikes for foods.

According to Wardlaw (1999) those who have reached the later part of their lives use less energy than before, because elderly people move less, foods that are rich in calories are not needed by them. The problem is that the quick snack enjoyed do not often provide enough minerals and vitamins.

The functioning of different body parts is connected with nutrition. As a person grows older, those part changes which in turn affect the process of food assimilation.

Eating a healthy diet can reduce the risk for many conditions associated with aging including anaemia, confusion, infections, hip fractures, hypotension and wounds. And when combined with

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regular physical activity it can reduce the risk of many chronic diseases, including osteoporosis, type 2 diabetes, heart diseases, stroke and some cancer (Reese 2007).

Many elderly people have unique barriers that prevent them from eating a healthy diet and engaging in regular physical activity. Difficulty chewing, a sensitive stomach, reduced appetite, and dietary restrictions are just a few of the barriers to healthy eating that the elderly experience.

A healthy eating plan for older adults include a variety of nutrient-rich foods. The 2005 Dietary Guidelines for Americans recommended a diet that emphasizes fruits, vegetables, whole grains and fat-free or low-fat dairy products. They also recommended a diet low in saturated and trans fats and rich in lean meats, beans and nuts (Reese 2007).

The bulk of the diet should include foods that are high in fiber like whole-grain breads and cereals, beans, fruits and vegetables. These foods can help prevent constipation as well as lower the risk for chronic diseases. Milk products are high in calcium and vitamin D, which helps keep bones strong in aging. Elderly people are at increased risk for nutrient deficiencies and should ensure adequate intake of calcium, vitamin D, folic acid, vitamin E, vitamin C, vitamin B12, magnesium, potassium and fiber (Turcotte 2006). It is important that the elderly have three servings of vitamins D fortified low fat / fat-free milk, yoghurt or cheese every day. Reduced lactose milk products, soy-based beverages or tofu are good alternatives for those who are lactose intolerant (Reese 2007).

Loneliness also contribute to decreased food intake. Many older adults would rather eat something convenient and unhealthy than cook for themselves and then eat it alone. Skipping meals is not healthy, and may cause the body metabolism to slow down or lead to eating more high-calorie, high-fat foods at the next meal or snack.

The thirst sensation decrease as one gets older and so the elderly may notice that they feel less thirsty. It's important to encourage plenty of water and water-based fluids. These include low-fat milk, decaffeinated coffee and tea and sports drinks, water-based foods like fruits vegetables and fruits are nutrient dense options. (Reese 2007)

Statement of the problem

Most elderly people are not aware of their nutrient requirement. They consume what is available or within their reach. Most of the time, they consume carbohydrate food which are cheap and accessible to them. Religion stops elderly from eating certain food. Some elderly don't see any reason for morning sunlight, some don't know the importance of fruits and vegetables in the diet.

Objective of the Study

To determine the food consumption pattern of elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State.

This study sought answers to the following research questions

- What is the food consumption pattern of the elderly in Ondo West Local Government?
- Do the elderly have any food taboo?
- Do they miss meals?
- Do they takes fruits and vegetables?
- Do they see any reason for morning sunlight?
- Do they takes snacks between meals?

Significance of the Study

This study will help both male and female elderly to know the nutrient requirements. It will shed light on food taboos of the elderly in Ondo West Local Government and their effects on their food consumption pattern. It will provide information on the food consumption pattern of the elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area and create room for improvement.

Scope of the Study

This study concentrated on food consumption pattern of the elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area.

Research Design and Methodology

The descriptive survey design was used to collect the data for the study.

Area of the Study

The study was carried out in five selected areas in Ondo town, these include: Odojomu , Okeagunla, Ijoka , Odosida, and Sora all in Ondo town.

Population of the Study

The population consisted of male and female, literate and non literate elderly in Ondo West Local Government.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

25 male and 25 female were randomly selected from each of the selected areas in Ondo West Local Government.

Research Instrument

The instrument used was interview method through open ended questionnaire which was divided into two sections A and B and respondents gave a 24-hour dietary recall of their food consumption.

Validation of Instrument

The questionnaire was prepared by the researcher and was validated by three experts to check the appropriateness of questionnaire before the instrument was administered.

Reliability of Instrument

The test-retest method was used, questionnaire was administered to the selected areas and a week later the same questionnaire was administered to the same set of people to obtain reliability of the instrument.

Data Collection

The questionnaire was administered by the researcher and given out to the respondents personally by her and all the questionnaires were collected back from the respondents.

Method of Data Analysis

The responses of respondents to the items of questionnaire were analyzed using simple frequencies and percentages.

Result, Data Analysis And Discussion

The relevant personal characteristics of the elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State as discovered during the research are as follows.

Table 1: Elderly Personal Characteristic

SEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Male	19	38
Female	31	62
Total	50	100

The Table 1 above shows number of male and female in the selected areas of Ondo West Local Government. Most of the respondents (62%) were female while 38% were male.

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Table 2: Distribution of the Respondents According to their Age Range

AGERANGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
50-55	22	44
55-60	15	30
60-65	9	18
70 and above	4	8
Total	50	100

This table shows the age range of the elderly in selected areas of Ondo West Local Government. The age range from 50-55 years was 44%, 50-60 years was 30%, 60 to 65 years was 18%, 70 and above was 8%. Most of the elderly (74%) in Ondo West Local Government Area were between 50 and 60 years old. Only 26% were above 60 years.

Table 3: Tribes of the Respondents

TRIBE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
YORUBA	37	74
IGBO	8	16
HAUSA	5	10
Total	50	100

The table above shows that most of the elderly (74%) were from Yoruba tribe, elderly from Igbo tribe were 16% and those from Hausa tribe were 10%.

Table 4: Educational Classification of Respondents

EDUCATIONALLEVEL	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Primary School Education	6	12
Modern III	3	6
Secondary School Education	12	24
Grade II	6	12
NCE/HND/OND	5	10
Graduate	8	16
Non Formal Education	10	20
Others	-	-
Total	50	100

This table shows that some of the respondent (24%) had secondary school education, those with primary school education (12%), those with modern III certificate were (6%), Grade II were (12%), NCE/HND/OND (10%), and Graduate were (16%). 80% of the elderly had at least primary school education.

Table 5: Classification of Respondents According to Occupation .

OCCUPATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Civil servant	14	28
Trader	17	34
Farmer	9	18
Retired	4	8
Others	6	12
Total	50	100

Table 5 above shows that most (62%) of the elderly in the selected areas of Ondo West Local Government were civil servant and traders, 18% were farmers, 8% were retired and 12% do others specified jobs such as musicians and artists.

Table 6: Exposure to early morning sunlight

	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	17	34
No	33	66
Total	50	100

This table shows how often the elderly in selected areas of Ondo West Local Government enjoy early morning sunlight. The table shows that 34% often enjoy early morning sunlight and 66% see no reason for early morning sunlight.

Table 7: Snacks Consumption between Meals

	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	26	52
No	24	48
Total	50	100

The table above shows that 52% of the elderly take snacks in between meals and 48% don't.

*The Food Consumption Pattern of the Elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State***Table 8: Food Consumption Pattern**

Meals	Breakfast		Lunch		Super	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Pounded yam / eba / amala / fufu	15	30	5	10	24	48
Egg / Tea and Bread	3	6	-	-	-	-
Rice only	5	19	4	8	10	20
Rice and beans	7	14	3	6	5	10
Yam / Cocoyam / Plantain	5	10	2	4	8	16
Beans only	4	8	2	4	-	-
Gari only	-	-	20	40	-	-
Pap	2	4	3	6	2	4
Potato / water yam	5	10	2	4	1	2
Others	3	6	4	8	-	-
No. of elderly who missed meals	1	2	5	10	-	-
Total	50	100	50	100	50	100

Table 8 shows that some 30% of the respondents take either pounded yam, amala, eba, fufu for their breakfast, 40% take gari only for lunch and 48% of the respondents take pounded yam, amala, eba or fufu for their supper. 6% take egg/tea and bread as breakfast. 14%, 6% and 10% take rice and beans as breakfast, lunch and supper respectively. 8% and 4% take beans only as breakfast and lunch respectively. 2% and 10% miss breakfast and lunch respectively

Table 9: Food Taboo of the Elderly

FOOD TABOO	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	38	76
No	12	24
Total	50	100

This table shows that most (76%) of the respondents have food taboo while 24% don't.

Discussion

Table 1 above shows that there are more females (62%) than males in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State. The elderly in this local government area see no reason (66%) for exposure to early morning sunlight as can be seen in Table 6 above. It is widely known however that the elderly are at increased risk for vitamin D deficiency (Turcotte 2006 and Reese 2007). The elderly (52%) takes snacks between meals as can be seen in Table 7 above. This may increase their ability to meet up with their nutrient requirement. Only 6% take egg/tea and bread as their breakfast (see table 8 above). This agrees with the findings of Okeke 1996 in his study on "Food consumption pattern and food preparation of Igbo people in Rural Nigerian Communities". He discovered that carbonated beverages, tea and coffee were rarely consumed by the Igbo people. Table 8 also shows that 63%, 28% and 74% take either pounded yam, eba, amala, fufu, rice, potato, pap or water yam as

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breakfast, lunch and supper respectively. 14%, 6% and 10% take rice and beans as breakfast, lunch and supper respectively. 8% and 4% take beans only as breakfast and lunch respectively. This also corresponds with Okeke 1996 discovery that starchy staples were the main foods consumed by the Igbo people and that the intake of protein-rich foods was limited by purchasing power and availability. Table 8 also shows that the elderly in this local government don't miss meals as 2% and 10% miss breakfast and lunch respectively.

Recommendations

Having been through all the aforementioned, the following are recommended:

- There should be a proper awareness of nutritional requirement for the elderly, because they consume what is available or within their reach and the more the nutritional problems they acquire.
- Due to the fact that most of the elderly are of no formal education, the guidance should be encouraged to transfer little knowledge acquired to their various homes. This will help to educate the elderly more on the needs to have a good food consumption pattern.
- Public talks, seminars and mass media should be employed to create awareness on the type of foods to be consumed by the elderly
- Health workers should be trained on the importance of proper nutrition for the elderly. These workers should visit the elderly to advise them and monitor adherence to the advise.

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